

Hydraulic activity of High Magnesian Portland Cement – Calcined Kaolinite Mix

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The effect of addition of calcined kaolinite on the hydraulic activity of high magnesian portland cement (MgO content upto 18%) has been investigated varying the proportions of calcined clay. It has been found that desirable hydraulic properties can be obtained by controlling the addition of calcined clay. The phases present in the hydrated and unhydrated cement have been identified using thermogravimetric method.

The presence of magnesia in portland cement beyond a certain limit makes the cement unstable. The free magnesia present in cement hydrates slowly with water to $Mg(OH)_2$ and this hydration is accompanied by volume expansion which ultimately causes disruption of concrete structure. The maximum allowable limit for stable portland cement has been fixed at 4–6% as per standard specifications¹. If the magnesia content in cement is more than 6%, except for a small amount, most of magnesia will remain as free, hard burnt, crystalline MgO (periclase) causing disruption of cement during hydration. For this reason, high calcium limestone with low MgO content is preferred as a raw material in cement industry. However, in India sources of low magnesian limestones are limited whereas high magnesian limestones are abundantly available.

The informations regarding the hydraulic properties and volume stability of high magnesian portland cement and use of clay as pozzolanic material are available². The aim of the present investigation is to improve the stability and hydraulic properties of high magnesian portland cement having magnesia content upto 18%, using some pozzolanic materials having reactive silica which will react with free crystalline magnesia. This is done by adding different amounts of calcined Rajmahal kaolinite with the high magnesian portland cement. The effects of addition of calcined clay as pozzolanic material on the properties of high magnesian portland cement have been studied.

Results and Discussion

The compositions of high magnesian portland cements

and an ordinary portland cement found by chemical analysis are shown in Table 1. The density values of all the cements are close to each other ranging from 2.91 to 3.31 $g\ cm^{-3}$. The density of the cement samples is found to increase slightly with increase in the magnesia content.

Setting time values of the cement samples are shown in Table 2. For all cement samples, with and without additive, the values are within the specified limits as per IS 4031-1968. It is found that the setting periods of high magnesian cements with and without additive are not much different, but are slightly higher than the corresponding initial and final setting periods of ordinary cement available from the market. So chemically combined magnesia makes the cement slow-setting.

The compressive strengths of all cement samples with and without additive and cured for different period of time are shown in the Table 3. For all cement samples there is a gradual increase of compressive strength with increase in hydration period. In most of the cases, the early strength of the cement samples are low in comparison to ordinary portland cement. The ultimate strength of high magnesian cement with additive is close to that of ordinary portland cement. The variation in the proportion of calcined kaolinite does not change the strength remarkably. So cement blended with the additive within the limit under study, may be used as portland cement substitute.

The results of DTGA of selected hydrated samples are shown in Fig. 1. The hydrated products have been characterised by different peaks obtained at different tem-

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION (% by wt.) OF CEMENT SAMPLES AND ADDITIVES*

Sample no.	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	L.O.I.	Density $g\ dm^{-3}$
Cement I	59.27	20.40	5.84	2.97	9.40	0.86	2.91
Cement II	55.95	19.92	5.82	3.05	13.21	0.88	3.12
Cement III	51.22	19.81	5.80	3.00	18.01	0.87	3.31
Cement (commercial)	62.00	22.14	5.80	2.44	3.80	0.81	3.20
Calcined Rajmahal kaolinite	Trace	53.89	45.01	0.49	Trace	Trace	—

* Rest. minor constituents like SO₃, TiO₂ and alkalis.

Fig. 1. DTGA curves of cement I with 35% kaolinite (900°) hydrated for different periods.

TABLE 2—SETTING TIME (min) DATA

Sample no.	Without additive	30% Kaolinite calcined at 900°
Cement I	Initial 160	165
	Final 300	310
Cement II	Initial 160	240
	Final 300	360
Cement III	Initial 165	165
	Final 365	310
Cement (commercial)	Initial 60	-
	Final 240	-

peratures (Table 4).

The autoclave expansion results of cement samples with and without additive are shown in Table 5. The results show that the autoclave expansion increases with increase in magnesia content of the cement samples without additive. The expansion values of the samples with additive are within limit (0.5%) and lower than that of the samples without additive.

Experimental

The cement clinkers were prepared from B.D.H. reagent grade chemicals such as $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, MgCO_3 , FeCl_3 and acid-washed 99.0% quartz. $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ was prepared by adding NH_4OH to FeCl_3 solution. Rajmahal kaolinite calcined at 900° for 2 h was used as additive.

Three batches of samples having different magnesia

TABLE 3—COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH VALUES (kg cm^{-2}) OF CEMENT AND CALCINED KAOLINITE (900°) MIXTURE HYDRATED FOR DIFFERENT PERIODS OF TIME

Hydration period days	Cement I				Cement II				Cement III				Portland cement
	0	25	30	35	Calcined Kaolinite content (%)				0	25	30	35	
3	7	50	52	66	17	99	97	97	3	31	10	35	116
7	10	83	114	114	19	114	126	126	11	55	10	48	155
14	41	140	131	126	36	145	136	136	21	116	18	107	230
28	97	155	184	155	97	155	174	155	121	194	42	174	273
180	126	271	281	315	121	271	223	294	131	271	218	232	350

TABLE 4—CHARACTERISATION OF DIFFERENT DTGA PEAKS

Temp. °C	Compound responsible*
100–140	Free moisture, silica gel
160–180	Taylor's hydrate I (0.8–1.5 $\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot \text{aq}$)
220–280	$3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$
420–440	$\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$
520–560	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
740–760	MgCO_3

* Ret. 12.

TABLE 5—EXPANSION RESULTS OF CEMENT SAMPLES

Sample no.	% Expansion
I	0.43
II	0.64
III	0.94
I + 30% Kaolinite	0.23
II + 30% Kaolinite	0.41
III + 30% Kaolinite	0.41

content (9–18%) were prepared by mixing stoichiometric quantities of raw materials subject to the following conditions: (i) composition was close to the ternary phase diagram $\text{CaO}-3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2-2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ invariant point and (ii) lime saturation factor and iron modulus were within the limits mentioned in IS : 269-1969.

The cement raw mixes were mixed with 0.5% B_2O_3 in the form of boric acid (to prevent β - γ -transformation of C_2S), and ground in a ball mill for 2 h. The mixture was then shaped to spherical balls using about 20% water, then dried, placed on a platinum basin and fired for 2 h in an electric furnace. For each batch, a particular clinkering temperature ($1300 \pm 20^\circ$) was employed. The clinker samples were quenched to room temperature and crushed in a mortar, then mixed with 5% (by wt.) gypsum (A.R., $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and ground in an iron pot mill for 2 h to a

fineness of about 3200–3500 $\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$. The calcined kaolinite having the same fineness as that of the cement was mixed separately with a part of each batch of cement in three different weight ratios, viz. 25, 30 and 35%.

The analysis of cement samples was done by IS : 269-1958 method. Density was measured according to IS : 269-1951 specification. Both initial and final setting times of cements were determined with Vicat needle apparatus as described in IS : 657 (1962) specification.

For the determination of compressive strength, 25.4 mm cubical briquettes were prepared in a steel mould by the method of Parker. The mortar consisted of prepared cements (with and without additive) and sand (20 to 50 mesh) in 1 : 3 proportion and mixed with 12.5% water. Compressive strengths of these briquettes cured under water for different periods of time (3, 7, 14, 28 and 180 days) were measured in a miniature hydraulic press. Differential thermogravimetric analyses (DTGA) of hydrated cements, with and without additives, were done with a uniform heating rate of 10°/min. The autoclave expansion test was performed on sample bar (2.5 in × 0.5 in × 0.5 in) following

ASTM4 specifications.

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